

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF PIRFENIDONE IN BULK AND MARKETED FORMULATION AND STUDY OF ITS DEGRADATION BEHAVIOUR BY UV-SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT:

A simple, precise, robust, and stability-indicating UV spectroscopic method was developed for the determination of Pirfenidone in bulk & its formulation, and to monitor the Degradation behaviour of the drug as per ICH Guidelines. Pirfenidone exhibited a maximum absorbance at 311nm in 50 v/v ethanol, which was selected as the analytical wavelength. The calibration curve exhibited a good linear relationship in the concentration range of 4-24µg/ml with a correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.9983. Precision was evaluated through intraday, interday variations with % RSD within 2. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.78 and 2.41µg/ml respectively. Accuracy was assessed through recovery and was in the range of 98-102%. The mean % assay was found to be 99.81. Degradation studies of Pirfenidone were well studied in all stress conditions, and the amount of degraded drug was calculated⁽¹⁻³⁾. The degradation products were monitored and characterized to understand the stability profile of Pirfenidone. This validated method can be readily applied for routine quality control analysis of Pirfenidone in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

KEYWORDS:

Degradation behaviour, Method development, Pirfenidone, Stability profile

I.INTRODUCTION:

Pirfenidone (PFD) is an oral, synthetic antifibrotic and anti-inflammatory drug used to treat idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), a chronic, progressive lung disease characterized by scarring¹. Chemically it is 5-methyl-1-phenyl-2-(1H)-Pyridine (fig. 1), and works mainly by reducing the production of certain proteins and growth factors that contribute to the development of fibrosis. It attenuates the production of growth factor – $\beta 1$ (Thf- β), a key profibrotic and pro-inflammatory cytokine implicated in IPF. Pirfenidone (ESBRIET) is the first drug to be licensed in Europe for the treatment of IPF²⁻³. In addition, it has a role as a non-narcotic analgesic, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug and an antipyretic⁴⁻⁸.

Fig 1: Chemical Structure of Pirfenidone

The review of the literature survey revealed that there are only a few reported methods for the estimation of Pirfenidone in biological samples⁹ and pharmaceutical formulation¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Under these conditions, we developed a simple, precise, and reliable stability indicating UV-spectrophotometric method for the quantification of Pirfenidone in bulk & pharmaceutical dosage form. The established method was validated in accordance with ICH Q2 R1 guidelines.

II.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The drug, Pirfenidone (PFD), was a sample of (purity- 99%) was obtained from Yarrow Chem products, Mumbai, India. The dosage form used in the present investigation was PIRFENIX, with a label claim of 200mg, bought from the local pharmacy. Ethanol (AR Grade) and distilled water (In-house prepared) were used in this study.

Shimadzu UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer 1800 Instrument (UV Probe Software, version 2.52) was used with a pair of 1 cm matched quartz cells was used in the study for recording the spectrum..

III.METHODOLOGY:

Selection of solvent:

To select a suitable solvent for the determination of Pirfenidone, various solvents were used such as Methanol, ethanol 50% v/v, Acetone, and Acetonitrile tested for solubility studies and it was found that PFD was freely soluble in ethanol 50% v/v, selected as a solvent.

Selection of Analytical wavelength:

The dilution was obtained to the concentration of 16 μg / ml for pirfenidone solution. The solution was scanned in UV range (200-400nm) in 10 mm Quartz cell against ethanol 50% v/v water blank. The study of spectrum revealed that pirfenidone show a well-defined λ_{max} at 311 nm (fig 2).

Preparation of standard solution:

PFD 10mg was precisely measured and added to 10ml volumetric flask. Add a few ml of ethanol 50% v/v to dissolve the drug and then make up to the mark. The obtained standard solution respective dilutions were prepared and used in the study.

Preparation of sample solution:

A stock solution (1000 µg / ml) was prepared by taking 10 tablets, crushed, powdered; weight equivalent to 1000 µg /ml of standard pirfenidone solution was taken and dissolved in a 10 ml volumetric flask using ethanol 50% v/v. From the clear test stock solution, pipette out 0.16 ml and make up to 10 ml with Double distilled water.

IV. VALIDATION OF THE METHOD:**Linearity and Range:**

Make to prepare six different concentrations in the range of 4-24 µg/ml of Pirfenidone, into a series of 10 ml standard volumetric flasks, and volumes were made up to mark with water. The absorbances were measured at 311nm against a solvent blank (ethanol:water;). The obtained absorbance values were plotted against the concentrations of Pirfenidone to get the calibration graphs.

Precision:

The precision was studied by analysis of multiple homogeneous samples. It is expressed as % RSD. Precision was carried out by intraday and interday variation studies. Intra-day Precision was carried, by analysing the sample solution taking measurements in different time intervals on the same day. While Inter-day Precision study was done by drawing measurements of sample solution on different days. The % RSD was calculated.

Detection Limit & Quantitation Limit:

The LOD and LOQ were based on the third approach and were calculated according to the $3.3\sigma/S$ and $10\sigma/S$ respectively; where σ is the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines and s is the slope of the calibration curve.

Robustness:

Robustness is the measure of the ability of a method to be unaffected by small changes in method parameters and gives an indication of its consistency. The method was altered to small changes in wavelength (± 3 nm) and solvent proportion (± 5 % v/v). The % RSD was calculated and noted.

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating the recovery of Pirfenidone by the standard addition method. The accuracy of the analytical method was assessed by determination of recovery for three concentrations corresponding to 50, 100 and 150 % of test solution concentration. For each concentration, three sets were prepared. The mean recovery of Pirfenidone was reported.

Force degradation studies:

Force degradation studies were conducted under various conditions, like acidic, alkaline, thermal, oxidation, and photolytic studies. The optimised concentration of Pirfenidone was taken from a stock solution (16 µg/ml) and subjected to 0.1M HCl and 0.1N NaOH in acid and alkali hydrolysis, and 3 % H₂O₂ in oxidative studies. The photolytic and thermal degradation were performed following the regulatory norms. The resulting solutions were taken and checked for their absorbance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The developed method was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines for various parameters as discussed below.

Linearity: The calibration plot of absorbance versus concentration was found to be linear over the concentration range of 4 to 24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ at 311nm, as shown in Fig 2 &3 and table 1 respectively. The correlation coefficient (r^2) has a value of 0.9982. Thus, indicating that test results were directly proportional to the amount (concentration) of analyte in the sample.

Table 1 Results of Linearity

S.NO	CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	ABSORBANCE
1	4	0.115
2	8	0.253
3	12	0.377
4	16	0.535
5	20	0.642
6	24	0.770

Fig 2: Overlay spectrum of PFD at 311nm

Fig 3: Calibration Curve of PFD

Precision:

The % RSD of assay results of six replicates should not be more than 2. The % RSD of the intra-day & interday studies was found to be 1.46 and 1.49. The results are tabulated in table 2 and hence the method was found precise.

Table 2: Results of Precision Study

S.NO	Intraday Precision (Absorbance)	Interday Precision (Absorbance)
1	0.548	0.550
2	0.535	0.537
3	0.533	0.535
4	0.550	0.534
5	0.551	0.551
6	0.548	0.548
Mean	0.544166667	0.540166667
Std Dev	0.007985403	0.008084965
% RSD	1.46	1.49

Accuracy:

The accuracy study was examined by the standard addition method testing the three unequal concentrations at 50, 100 & 150% levels of PFD. The mean % recovery was found within the range of 98–100 as shown in table 3.

Table:3 Accuracy Studies

S.No	Spike Level (%)	Absorbance	Amount Added (µg/ml)	Amount Found (µg/ml)	% Recovery	%Mean Recovery
1	50	0.265	8.00	7.29	99.03	99.16
2		0.263		7.86	98.28	
3		0.268		8.01	100.15	
4	100	0.537	16.00	16.05	100.34	100.78
5		0.540		16.14	100.90	
6		0.541		16.17	101.09	
7	150	0.791	24.00	23.65	98.53	98.49
8		0.791		23.65	98.53	
9		0.790		23.62	98.41	

LOD AND LOQ:

The limit detection and limit of quantification was calculated from the slope and standard deviation of the precision study and found as 0.78 and 2.41 µg/ml respectively.

Robustness:

The change in the wavelength and solvent proportion with the same concentration of 16µg/ml gave reproducible results. Hence the parameters were found to be robust as stated in table 4.

Table 4 Robustness values

S.No	Parameter	Wavelength (Nm)	Absorbance ± Std. Deviation (N=3)	% Rsd
1	Wavelength (±3nm)	308nm	0.541 ± 0.005686	1.04
2		311nm*	0.532 ± 0.006658	1.24
3		314nm	0.533 ± 0.00611	1.14
4	Solvent Proportion (±5% v/v)	45%	0.549 ± 0.001155	0.21
5		50%*	0.548 ± 0.001528	0.27
6		55%	0.539 ± 0.0025082	0.38

Assay:

It was done by adopting the procedure for the preparation of the sample solution as presented in the validation of methods. The % purity of PFD was found within 98-102%

Stability Studies:

The drug was subjected to all the degradation conditions, such as Acid, Base, Oxidation, Photolytic, & Thermal studies & found to be stable under all conditions.

Table 5: Results of stability studies

S.No	Stress Conditions	Absorbance	Purity (%)	Degradation(%)
1	0.1 HCl	0.493	92.14	7.86
2	0.1 NaOH	0.488	91.21	8.79
3	Peroxide (H ₂ O ₂) 3.0% v/v	0.497	92.89	7.11
4	Thermal (70 ⁰ c)	0.505	94.39	5.61
5	Photolytic (UV)	0.514	96.07	3.93

VI. CONCLUSION:

The developed UV spectroscopic method was found to be simple, precise, accurate, and robust for the determination of Pirfenidone in bulk and its dosage form. The method was specific while estimating the commercial formulation and found no interference of excipients and other additives. The proposed method for the stability study shows that there is appreciable degradation found in the stress condition. Statistical analysis for the results clearly demonstrates that the method is suitable for the degradation products, and thus the method can be considered as a stability-indicating method and can be used for routine use in quality control industry laboratories.

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